

Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud

Project Number: 823782

Start Date of Project: 01/01/2019

Duration: 40 months

Deliverable 6.6 SSHOC Final Conference Report

Dissemination Level	PU
Due Date of Deliverable	31/03/22, M39
Actual Submission Date	26/04/22
Work Package	WP6 - Fostering Communities, Empowering Users, & Building Expertise
Task	Task 6.2 Fostering Communities: Engaging New & Existing Users
Type	Report
Approval Status	Approved by EC - 27 April 2022
Version	V1.0
Number of Pages	p.1 – p.83

Abstract:

This report describes the organisation and outcomes of the SSHOC Final Conference that took place on 6 and 7 April 2022, in a hybrid format in Brussels, Belgium.

The information in this document reflects only the author's views and the European Community is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained therein. The information in this document is provided "as is" without guarantee or warranty of any kind, express or implied, including but not limited to the fitness of the information for a particular purpose. The user thereof uses the information at his/ her sole risk and liability. This deliverable is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License.

History

Version	Date	Reason	Revised by
0.1	21/04/2022	First version	Rosie Allison, Ana Inkret, Irena Vipavc Brvar
0.1	22/04/2022	Peer review	Veronika Heider, Simon Saldner, Andreas Villarreal
0.2	22/04/2022	Address peer review comments, send to coordination	Rosie Allison, Ana Inkret
0.3	22/04/2022	Formatting	Ana Inkret
1.0	26/04/2022	Version for submission	

Author List

Organisation	Name	Contact Information
LIBER	Rosie Allison	rosie.allison@libereurope.org
CESSDA/UL-FDV	Ana Inkret	ana.inkret@fdv.uni-lj.si
CESSDA/UL-FDV	Irena Vipavc Brvar	irena.vipavc@fdv.uni-lj.si

Contributors

Organisation	Name	Contact Information
GESIS	Libby Bishop	ElizabethLea.Bishop@gesis.org
CESSDA	Martina Draščić Capar	martina.drascic@cessda.eu
DANS KNAW	Vasso Kalaitzi	vasso.kalaitzi@dans.knaw.nl
CESSDA	Vanja Komljenović	vanja.komljenovic@cessda.eu
Trust-IT	Rita Meneses	r.meneses@trust-itservices.com
Trust-IT	Stephanie Parker	s.parker@trust-itservices.com
CESSDA	Panagiota Starida	panagiota.starida@cessda.eu
Trust-IT	Marieke Willems	m.willems@trust-itservices.com

Executive Summary

The report covers the organisation, delivery, content, and lessons learned from the SSHOC Final Conference, titled **“Advancing SSH Research with SSHOCingly good and sustainable resources”**. The hybrid conference took place at Bluepoint premises in Brussels, Belgium, on 6 and 7 April 2022.

Task 6.2 and WP2 lead the organisation of the conference with the support of the project partners in the organising and programme committees.

The aims of the conference were to showcase the project achievements, discuss their impact for the SSH community, build participants’ knowledge on the developed tools and services, and engage with a broad range of SSHOC stakeholders and European research initiatives. The conference programme included four plenary sessions, a policymaking discussion, six parallel sessions, networking and social activities, and an online challenge for users of SSHOC tools and services. The materials and video recordings of the sessions are available online.

Abbreviations and Acronyms

CNR	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche/National Research Council
EC	European Commission
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
LMS	Learning management system
MCSQ	Multilingual Corpus of Survey Questionnaires
MoU	Memorandum of Understanding
RDA	Research Data Alliance
RI	Research Infrastructure
SSH	Social Science and Humanities
SSHOC	Social Science and Humanities Open Cloud
TDR	Trusted Digital Repository
UN SDG	United Nations Sustainable Development Goals
WP	Work package
WP2	Work package 2 - Communication, Dissemination, and Impact
WP6	Work package 6 - Fostering Communities & Building Expertise

Table of Contents

1. Introduction	5
2. Organisation	5
2.1 Defining the framework	5
2.2 Programme committee	6
2.3 Organising committee	6
2.4 SSHOC'n Tell Challenge	8
3. Conference content	11
3.1 Sessions	11
3.1.1 Final agenda	11
3.1.2 Summary of the sessions	14
3.4 SSHOC'n Tell Challenge	23
4. Results	25
4.1 Participants	25
4.2 Participant feedback	29
4.3 Lessons learned	32
5. Conclusion	33
6. References	34
Appendix 1 - SSHOC'n Tell Challenge Starter Kit	36
Appendix 2 - Quizz questions and response	58
Appendix 3 - SSHOC'n Tell Challenge FINAL REPORT	69
Appendix 4 - Excerpts from the post-event survey	80

1. Introduction

This report concerns the organisation, delivery, and outcomes of the hybrid final conference of the SSHOC project, titled “Advancing SSH Research with SSHOCingly good and sustainable resources”. Organisation and delivery of the conference was part of the task 6.2 *Fostering Communities: Engaging New & Existing Users*. It was co-organised in collaboration with work package 2 - *Communication, Dissemination, and Impact*, with support and participation of many project partners in all WPs.

The conference was planned as a cross-stakeholder event with the goal of showcasing the project achievements, building participants’ knowledge on the developed tools and services, and engaging with a broad range of SSHOC stakeholders and European research initiatives.¹

The conference took place on 6 and 7 April 2022, in a hybrid format in Brussels, Belgium. The programme included four panel sessions, six parallel sessions, social events, and the parallel online event SSHOC’n Tell Challenge.² This report illustrates how the structure and content of the conference was conceived and executed and culminates in an evaluation based on the observations of the organising committee and participant feedback.

2. Organisation

2.1 Defining the framework

The final conference was an opportunity to bring together a broad range of SSHOC stakeholders, engage them with the achievements of the project, and discuss the future and sustainability of both the results and the community. The intention was to focus on the impact that the project has had, and will continue to have, on the SSH community.

After a long period of meetings and events held online due to the COVID-19 pandemic, it was decided early on that the final conference would have a face-to-face component, as much as the health situation would allow at the time. Numerous online training events, discussion panels, workshops, webinars, and an online conference³ equipped the project team with important skills in holding online events and engaging with the participants remotely. The partners and organisers were, however, not inclined to

¹ Martina Torma, Vasso Kalaitzi, Elly Dijk, Marion Wittenberg, Marieke Willems, Darja Fiser, Kristina Pahor de Maiti, Matej Durco, & Irena Vipavc Brvar. (2019a). SSHOC D6.2 Building Expertise Strategy (v1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4558294>

² Conference website: <https://www.sshopencloud.eu/events/sshoc-final-conference>. Last accessed 12/04/2022.

³ These events have been documented in previous project deliverables: *D6.12 Report on the SSHOC train-the-trainer bootcamps* (Fišer et al. 2021), *D6.3 Final report on the outcome of the awareness raising workshops* (Inkret et al. 2021), *D6.4 Report on awareness webinars* (Inkret et al. 2022), and *D6.5 Report on Stakeholder Series events* (Vipavc Brvar et al. 2021).

waive the added value of meeting in person: the possibility to forge new or deeper connections, network on a more informal level, communicate without technical filters or delays, and celebrate the achievements in the company of peers and wider community.

Yet the project team also appreciated the numerous benefits that remote participation holds: namely the accessibility and inclusivity of the online events for both participants and speakers. These considerations, coupled with the persisting obstacles for travel, ultimately led to the choice of a hybrid format. In the last months before the start of the conference, the initial team of WP2 and T6.2 connected with the project partners and split the work into two planning committees; the programme committee and the organising committee.

2.2 Programme committee

The programme committee consisted of the leaders of WP2 and T6.2, and WP leaders or their representatives as the content experts. WP leaders and representatives acted as the link to the members of each WP, ensuring that all partners were able to participate and had a say in the structure of the agenda and presentation of their work. The programme committee ensured that the conference programme focused on the impact of the SSHOC results, addressed their sustainability, and facilitated a discussion with policymakers.

The planning of the conference agenda began by mapping the work of the WPs to the planned project contributions to EOSC, defined in the ESFRI clusters' Position Paper.⁴ This approach allowed for multidisciplinary sessions that reached across WPs. Once the draft agenda was confirmed by the WPs, the programme committee appointed session owners - organisers - who proceeded to fine-tune the session structure, liaised with the speakers, and, in most cases, took the role of session chairs or moderators.

Programme committee members were Laure Barbot (DARIAH), Martina Draščić Capar (CESSDA), Daan Broeder (CLARIN), Carmen DiMeo (CNR), Edward Gray (CNRS), Veronika Heider (AUSSDA), Ivana Ilijašić Veršić (CESSDA), Ana Inkret (UL/FDV-ADP), Mari Kleemola (FSD), Vanja Komljenović (CESSDA), Monica Monachini (CNR), Daniela Negoita (TiU-EVS), Stephanie Parker (Trust-IT), Astrid Verheusen (LIBER), Irena Vipavc Brvar (UL/FDV-ADP), Marieke Willems (Trust-IT), and Tatsiana Yankelevich (LIBER).

2.3 Organising committee

This committee was composed of representatives from project members of CESSDA, UL/FDV-ADP, Trust-IT, GESIS, and AUSSDA. It was tasked with organising the logistical aspects of the conference, including:

- keeping track of budget,

⁴ Gotz, Andy, Petzold, Andreas, Asmi, Ari, Blomberg, Niklas, Lamanna, Giovanni, & Dekker, Ron. (2020). ESFRI cluster projects - Position papers on expectations and planned contributions to the EOSC. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3675081>

- liaising with the chosen venue,
- identifying and assigning event roles,
- overseeing the organisation and delivery of the sessions,
- overseeing the reception desk,
- the creation and management of event materials,
- content of the event website,
- working with WP2 on the communication of the event (prior, during, and after),
- social programme (quiz),
- post event wrap up.

Once the decision to run a hybrid conference was made, the organising committee were tasked with finding a suitable venue that could accommodate such an event. Several quotes were obtained from venues in the Brussels region, with the final decision being based on the suitability of the venue to supply technical support, budgeting restraints, capacity, and accessibility. The venue Bluepoint⁵ was chosen as the best option.

The organising committee were instrumental in ensuring the sessions (put together by the programme committee and project WP members) were consistent in appearance and tone, and that all sessions were geared towards the focus of the conference: illustrating SSHOC outputs, sustainability, and impact. Templates for presentations and a uniform session structure were developed to achieve this aim. The organising committee maintained close communication with sessions organisers (responsible for bringing together the speakers for each session) to ensure that the conference was coherent in structure.

One challenge of the hybrid format was identifying and assigning the numerous roles to be covered to ensure the event ran smoothly. Staff from Bluepoint covered the manning of technical equipment, but the organisation committee was tasked with covering the following roles for each session:

- Chat checker to liaise with the online participants
- Session rapporteurs for post-event reporting (several partners who were not members of the organising committee stepped in)
- Technical support for online speakers
- Social media coverage

These tasks were split between members of the organising committee and other volunteers from the project members.

Event materials were another vital aspect of ensuring a good experience for participants. “Welcome packs” for the in-person participants were prepared based on the feedback from project partners during the previous general project meeting and were appropriately branded.

⁵ Bluepoint website, <https://www.bluepoint.be/nl/brussel/>. Last accessed 20/04/2022.

An important addition to the welcome pack was the Legacy Booklet.⁶ This collection of resources showcased the work performed by SSHOC partners to achieve its open, multidisciplinary approach, and presented factsheets to cover the project Key Exploitable Results, with each factsheet offering an overview of the results, how to use them and where to access them. Other conference materials included:

- SSHOC welcome pack with cap, reusable mug, badge and lanyard with name tag
- Programme flyer (paper and online)
- Venue signage
- Advertising banners (for the conference and SSHOC'n Tell Challenge)
- Partner testimonial videos (to be played during breaks for the online audience)

The organising committee worked closely with the project's communication team to ensure a good number of participants were attracted to the conference, using various means of distribution including online channels (e.g., social media), direct mailing to interested stakeholders, and the utilisation of project members' networks.

To ensure the outputs of the conference were widely shared, the organising committee also took on responsibility for post-event activities such as the release of event recordings, presentations, and news pieces and reporting.

Organising committee members were: Martina Draščić Capar (CESSDA), Astrid Verheusen (LIBER), Athina Papadopoulou (LIBER), Tatsiana Yankelevich (LIBER), Rosie Allison (LIBER), Andrej Vrčon (LIBER), Irena Vipavc Brvar (UL/FDV-ADP), Ana Inkret (UL/FDV-ADP), Marieke Willems (Trust-IT), Filomena Minichiello (Trust-IT), Serenella Muradoregallas (Trust-IT) and Andreas Villarreal (AUSSDA).

2.4 SSHOC'n Tell Challenge

As one of the engagement and end-user onboarding mechanisms for the final conference, the consortium organised a "challenge" to provide end-users the opportunity to try out the SSHOC tools through a competition-based exercise. The general aims of the challenge were to:

- Raise awareness of the added value of SSHOC tools and to get people testing the tools in a hands-on session,
- Onboard end-users via the Data Communities (WP9 + ESFRIs),
- Produce user stories.

Participants were required to work on a predefined challenge on one of four topics:

- **TOPIC 1 - Virtual Collection Registry and Switchboard**
 - Challenge 1A - How might we adapt the Virtual Collection Registry for other research domains? What features would be necessary to scale up the use of the VCR?

⁶ SSHOC. (2022). SSHOC Legacy booklet. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6394462>

- Challenge 1B - What tools and services might be added to the Switchboard to make it useful for other research domains? Where should the Switchboard be visible/accessible in your research data domain?
- **TOPIC 2 - SSH Open Marketplace**
 - Challenge 2A - Make the tools and resources of your community visible
 - Challenge 2B - Create a living memory of what the best research practices in your given community should be
 - Challenge 2C - Reuse the SSH Open Marketplace data using the Application Programming Interface (API)
- **TOPIC 3- TRAINING**
 - CHALLENGE 3A - I am preparing a training session on Open Science and looking for materials to reuse. Can I find these materials using the Training Discovery Toolkit (TDT) - and how can I reuse them?
 - CHALLENGE 3B - I am working on a training session but am struggling to make it interactive. How can I use the Training Discovery Toolkit to achieve this goal?
 - CHALLENGE 3C - Play the SSHOC League of Data and learn how to Archive and Publish your research data.
- **TOPIC 4 - WILDCARD - Advance your own research**
 - Challenge 4 - How would you use any of the available SSHOC tools to advance your own research? To answer your research question?

Over the two days of the conference, participants were asked to develop a user story and deliver it in two milestones:

- Milestone 1: a (maximum) 1-page summary that provides a general description of the user story, summarising its goal.
- Milestone 2: a (maximum) 7-slide presentation that describes the user story.

The second milestone was delivered by participants during the SSHOC'n Tell User Stories Parade session that took place before the final wrap-up of the conference, to illustrate how SSHOC tools can be used in real-life SSH research.

The organising committee sourced mentors (members of SSHOC consortium with expertise in the tools that were used during the challenge) and jointly defined and developed the necessary tools for the challenge (namely the Starters Kit⁷). Judges who would determine the winning team were named as well.

The logistics of running the challenge, including the provision of the platform and technical support for participants, was undertaken by the online Hackathon agency KreativDistrikt⁸. A page on the platform

⁷ Starter kit for the participants,

https://docs.google.com/document/d/1CTv1Mdp8VmFmvox_cAktPnA5UKEVK0Ja/edit#. See also Appendix 1.

⁸ KreativDistrikt website, <https://www.kreativdistrikt.com/>. Last accessed 19/04/2022.

Eventornado⁹ was used as a means for participants to communicate with each other and with the mentors, and to source information for and submit their user stories. A pre-challenge info session¹⁰ (1st April) was conducted to familiarise participants with the challenge structure and tools (lead by KreativDistrikt).

To encourage participation, the organisers determined a list of prizes for the winning teams. The prizes were as follows:

- Joint publication (with the mentor institution) publishing costs will be paid for
- In-house training - up to 4 hours
- In-house implementation support or SSH Open Marketplace onboarding of the winner's organisation's SSH resource that meets the requirements, total effort available up to 4 hours
- Amazon gift vouchers winner 1K, 2nd and 3rd place 500€ each team.

Prizes were awarded upon an evaluation by three judges - SSHOC consortium members Holly Wright, Karla Boesma and Veronika Heider - based on the following criteria:

- How effectively was the challenge addressed with the use of SSHOC tools?
- How engaging is the user story told in the Milestones?
- How inspiring are the tips & tricks for potential users?
- How realistic are the recommendations for future improvement?

A full list of participation conditions and rules, as developed by the organisers in cooperation with KreativDistrikt, can be found in the Terms and Conditions¹¹.

⁹ SSHOC'n Tell Challenge website, <https://eventornado.com/event/sshocntellchallenge#home>. Last accessed 19/04

¹⁰ Recording of the info session, <https://youtu.be/Mn6wmewabeQ>. Last accessed 19/04

¹¹ Terms, Conditions and Participation Agreement for the SSHOC'n Tell Challenge, <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1F4yCkntanetw0TFbt5yYF-IHMZrfpBndzUaDoAZMHxs/edit?usp=sharing>.

3. Conference content

3.1 Sessions

3.1.1 Final agenda

Wednesday, 6 April 2022

8:30 - 9:00	<i>Welcome Coffee, Registration and Online Meeting Point</i>	
09:00 - 10:00	<p>Welcome Plenary: Connecting the Dots for SSH implementation in EOSC Start the day with multi-faceted views on SSH and complementary EU initiatives Presentation Moderator: <i>Marieke Willems (Trust-IT)</i> ESFRI point of view - <i>Ivana Ilijasic Versic (CESSDA)</i> EC & EOSC point of view - <i>Blagovesta Cholova (European Research Executive Agency, Unit REA.C4)</i> Researcher point of view - <i>Edward J. Gray (Huma-Num CNRS, DARIAH ERIC)</i></p>	<p>SSHOC'n Tell Challenge!</p> <p>Try out our tools and tell your user story.</p> <p>Online & Room: Galilei</p> <p><i>Moderated by Irena Vipavc Brvar (UL-FDV/ADP) and Michele Erba (Kreativdistrikt)</i></p> <p>Video recording</p>
10:00 - 10:30	<i>Networking Coffee</i>	<p>SSHOC Policymaking discussion - invitation only Room: Baekeland</p>
10:30 - 12:00	<p>Discovery gateways and the SSH Open Marketplace</p> <p>Join fellow intrepid explorers for a tour of SSH synergies in the EOSC Context Presentation</p> <p>Moderator: <i>Edward J. Gray (CNRS, DARIAH)</i> Launch of SSH Open Marketplace - <i>Matej Ďurčo (OEAW, DARIAH)</i> EOSC Portal, the universal access channel to EOSC services and resources - <i>Matthew Viljoen (EGI, EOSC Future)</i> GoTriple - <i>Yannick Legré (OPERAS)</i> Discover inspiring cultural heritage at Europeana - <i>Valentine Charles (Europeana)</i> Data Catalogues in SSHOC - <i>Carsten Thiel (CESSDA)</i></p>	
12:00 - 13:00	<i>Networking Lunch</i>	

13:00 - 14:30	<p>Parallel session 1 Opportunities for cross-disciplinary Interoperability in SSH research data management Presentation</p> <p>Moderator: <i>Daan Broeder (CLARIN)</i> ConversionHub - <i>Mari Kleemola (Tampere University, CESSDA)</i> Switchboard - <i>Claus Zinn (CLARIN)</i> Virtual Collection Registry - <i>Willem Elbers (CLARIN)</i> SSH Vocabulary Platform - <i>Matej Ďurčo (OEAW, DARIAH)</i></p>	<p>Parallel session 2 Multilingualism: A tour of new SSH research enablers Presentation</p> <p>Moderator: <i>Francesca Frontini (CNR, CLARIN)</i> Machine translation for multilingual terminologies - <i>Francesca Frontini (CNR)</i> Prototype for TDM and statistical analysis on legal texts - <i>Daniela Ceccon (WageIndicator)</i> Automatic verification - <i>Yuri Pettinicchi (SHARE)</i> Ethnic Minorities and Migration Question DataBank - <i>Ami Saji (SciencesPo)</i></p>
14:30 - 15:00	<i>Networking Coffee</i>	
15:00 - 16:30	<p>Parallel session 3 In practice: interoperability and data management in SSH Presentation</p> <p>Moderator: <i>Emiliano Degl'Innocenti (CNR, E-RIHS)</i> Platforms for GLAM institutions: - AiOLI - <i>Adeline Manuel (CNRS)</i> - RESTORE - <i>Emiliano Degl'Innocenti, Carmen Di Meo, Francesco Coradeschi, Maurizio Sanesi, OVI Research Fellows (CNR, OVI)</i> Citation prototype as a data management tool - <i>Nicolas Larousse (CNRS, DARIAH), Cesare Concordia (CNR, ISTI)</i> The Web Panel Sample Service (WPSS) for cross-national surveys and panels - <i>Gianmaria Bottoni (ESS Survey), Geneviève Michaud (SciencesPO, CDSP)</i> The 'Archive in a Box', based on Dataverse - <i>Marion Wittenberg & Vyacheslav Tykhonov (DANS-KNAW)</i></p>	<p>Parallel session 4 SSHOC practical prompts for data and research Presentation</p> <p>Moderator: <i>Daniela Negoita (Tilburg University)</i> New ESS data repository: Recommendations for a FAIR compliant integrated data and metadata repository - <i>Archana Bidargaddi (Norwegian Agency for Shared Services in Education and Research)</i> Adding biomedical data to the SHARE repository - <i>Fabio Franzese (Max Planck Institute for Social Law and Social Policy, SHARE)</i> surveycodings.org - <i>Rodrigo Reyes (European Values Study, Tilburg University)</i> The Multilingual Corpus of Survey Questionnaires - <i>Lidun Hareide (Møreforsking)</i></p>
16:30 - 17:30	<i>Quizz & Networking drinks with our on- and offline guests (Moderated by Irena Vipavc Brvar, UL-FDV/ADP)</i>	
17:00 - 20:00	Social dinner	

Thursday, 07th April 2022

09:00 - 10:30	<p>Opening plenary: Breaking down silos on the road to the SSH Open Cluster Presentation</p> <p>Moderator: <i>Astrid Verheusen (LIBER)</i> Bridging the silos & cross disciplinary use of tools - <i>Cees van der Eijk (The University of Nottingham)</i> The SSH Open Cluster, future collaboration and a Memorandum of Understanding - <i>Ivana Ilijasic Versic (CESSDA, SSHOC)</i> SSHOC Governance and Sustainability - <i>Franciska de Jong (CLARIN)</i> SSH Open Marketplace Governance - <i>Laure Barbot (DARIAH)</i></p>		<p>SSHOC'n Tell Challenge! Try out our tools and tell your user story.</p> <p>Online & Room: Galilei</p>
10:30 - 11:00	<p><i>Networking Coffee</i></p>		
11:00 - 12:30	<p>Parallel session 5</p> <p>Deep dive: training resources FAIRification, community and future opportunities SSHOC Training in conversation with the wider ecosystem Presentation Video Recording Moderator: <i>Ricarda Braukmann (DANS, SSHOC)</i> <i>Elizabeth Newbold (STFC)</i> <i>Ellen Leenarts (SSHOC, DANS)</i> <i>Iulianna van der Lek (SSHOC, CLARIN)</i> <i>Shanmugasundaram Venkataraman (EOSC Future, OpenAIRE)</i> <i>Irena Vipavc Brvar (Univerza v Ljubljani, CESSDA)</i></p>	<p>Parallel session 6</p> <p>How to become a SSHOCingly trustworthy environment for SSH data. Tips & tricks for Research Infrastructures Presentation Video Recording Moderator: <i>Mari Kleemola (Tampere University, CESSDA)</i> SSHOC Trusted Repositories user stories and certification issues for specific communities - <i>Henri Ala-Lahti (Tampere University, CESSDA)</i> Initiate to create SSH GDPR Code of Conduct and legal data protection issues - <i>Marianne Høgetveit Myhren (SIKT, NSD)</i> GESIS and UKDA Pilot on secure connection - <i>Deborah Wiltshire (GESIS)</i> Opening access to research data in the archaeology domain - <i>Holly Wright (University of York)</i></p>	
12:30 - 13:30	<p>Networking Lunch and Interactive Session with online guests</p>		
13:30 - 14:30	<p>SSHOC'n Tell User Stories Parade (Moderated by <i>Irena Vipavc Brvar (UL-FDV/ADP)</i> and <i>Michele Erba (Kreativdistrikt)</i>) Video Recording</p>		

14:30 - 16:30	<p>AfterSSHOC: synergies along the journey to EOSC and a view into the future An interactive panel discussion on the added value for researchers, governance, collaboration in EOSC and a collaborative future. Presentation</p> <p>Moderator: <i>Ivana Ilijasic Versic (CESSDA, SSHOC)</i> Reporting back on Policy Discussions. Collaboration opportunities after SSHOC and Agreements - <i>Franciska de Jong (CLARIN)</i> ESFRI Cluster projects - <i>Giovanni Lamanna (ESCAPE)</i> EOSC Association - <i>Ute Gunsenheimer (EOSC Association)</i> EOSC Future - <i>Ron Dekker (Technopolis Group, EOSC Future)</i> Data Communities - <i>Laura Morales (SciencesPo, SSHOC, Member of EOSC Researcher Engagement & Adoption Task Force, EOSC Future User Group)</i> Panel discussion with: <i>Franciska de Jong (CLARIN), Giovanni Lamanna (ESCAPE), Rudolf Dimper (PANOSC), Ute Gunsenheimer (EOSC Association), Ron Dekker (Technopolis Group, EOSC Future) and Laura Morales (SciencesPo, SSHOC, Member of EOSC Researcher Engagement & Adoption Task Force, EOSC Future User Group)</i></p> <p>SSHOC Final Conference wrap up</p>
---------------	--

Agenda is also available online.¹²

3.1.2 Summary of the sessions

WELCOME PLENARY: CONNECTING THE DOTS FOR SSH IMPLEMENTATION IN EOSC

Organiser and moderator	Marieke Willems (Trust-IT)
Main takeaways and considerations for the future	<p>Share SSHOC with your own communities to keep the tools and services alive (Ivana Ilijašić Veršić, CESSDA and SSHOC Coordinator)</p> <p>The research infrastructures will still be here in 5 year's time and beyond. This is what EOSC was designed for. The priority for the European Commission is to focus on the next steps in terms of researcher needs, now and in the future (Blagovesta Cholova, European Commission and SSHOC Project Officer)</p> <p>We must meet the needs of SSH researchers, know where the researchers are, who they are and what they need. We shouldn't blind them with European infrastructure terminology. Our role is to make sure we impactfully reach them and enable them to do their research in the digital world (Edward Gray, Huma-Num CNRS, DARIAH ERIC)</p>

¹² Agenda for SSHOC Final Conference, <https://www.sshopencloud.eu/agenda-sshoc-final-conference>. Last accessed 12/04/202.

Links to materials	Slides: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6446101
	Video recording: https://youtu.be/0TdcMgaW3tM

DISCOVERY GATEWAYS AND THE SSH OPEN MARKETPLACE

Organiser and moderator	Edward J. Gray, CNRS, DARIAH
Main takeaways and considerations for the future	<p>SSH Open Marketplace is one of the key SSHOC services - a discovery platform that curates and contextualises tools and services for SSH researchers by linking them with related publications, datasets, training materials, and workflows. Three guiding principles in creating the SSH Open Marketplace were contextualisation, curation, and community: trusted sources, assuring the quality of metadata that is crucial for update and usage; involving the community, but balancing between curation and contributions from the community.</p> <p>EOSC Portal is a gateway for information on EOSC. For users, it is an entrypoint for discovering and accessing resources via the EOSC Portal Catalogue and Marketplace; service providers can onboard resources and find new users on the Portal.</p> <p>GoTRIPLE is a multilingual discovery platform for social sciences and humanities, based on the Isidore search engine. It offers a single-entry point for exploring, discovering, and accessing literature, data, projects and researcher profiles at European level, across subject and language boundaries.</p> <p>Europeana hosts over 51 million of digital objects from the cultural heritage sector. Materials are diverse and multilingual; quality criteria for content and metadata have been established. Users can access the data through many entry points. Europeana also focuses on capacity building.</p> <p>SSH data is available through various data catalogues that often have institutional basis, are designed for domain data and focus on target users. The challenge lies in finding the balance between specific discovery portals and catalogues with a wide variety of data, and clarifying who these are targeting.</p>
Links to materials	Slides: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6446517
	Video recording: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=SSijH0nsz0A

SSHOC POLICYMAKING DISCUSSION

Organiser and moderator	Ivana Ilijašić Veršić, CESSDA
Main takeaways and considerations for the future	<p>Sustainability of the clusters is a must: even though we are “ending a project”, the current phase is the starting point to develop more substantial collaboration and communication, to keep working together on a federated service offer, and use the Marketplace as our common shop window. We are ready for the next level but we also need to keep an individual level of RIs operation, and focus on our existing missions (aligns well with the model of network of repositories).</p> <p>The need for a structured dialogue with stakeholders: clusters have proved that they can do it within and outside of clusters. EC expects clusters to show how they can promote activities more at the policy level.</p> <p>Need for stable support (funding) for the communication and activities built up through the projects (EC supporting this form of work and finding new models of support).</p> <p>Emerging request from the EC: how to track down the impact of the results and the uptake also beyond academia (contribution to overall digital transformation); to be incorporated in the next programme. Pay attention here to uptake in research communities (resulting in implementation Open Science principles); impact to society (i.e. COVID-response; projects in EOSC Future run by SSH RIs; relation to UN SDGs).</p> <p>EOSC Association also recognises the high value of the thematic angle provided by the clusters as without thematic services there is no EOSC. Communication channels with clusters will be set up.</p> <p>The discussion was invitation-only and was not recorded.</p>

PARALLEL SESSION 1: OPPORTUNITIES FOR CROSS-DISCIPLINARY INTEROPERABILITY IN SSH RESEARCH DATA MANAGEMENT

Organiser and moderator	Daan Broeder, CLARIN
Main takeaways and considerations for the future	<p>Although Interoperability requires various kinds of standardisation, there are good reasons for discipline diversity. These have to be accepted and worked with, not overridden (e.g. domain specific metadata standards).</p> <p>Good collaboration with researchers helps to produce tools that support actual work practices in research, e.g. a virtual collection tool that searches across domains, and enables the collection of the actual data/resources, not only links or metadata to those sources.</p>

	<p>Vocabulary is the semantic glue that allows cross domain understanding, so vocabularies should also be FAIR.</p> <p>More machine actionable content is needed, e.g. for Vocabulary commons.</p> <p>Sustainability is still a challenge - some of the RIs are sustained but by individual institutions. Different funding models could address this question.</p> <p>There is an ongoing tension of scaling - what to centralise (vocabulary ownership) vs. what has to remain decentralised to support very different communities.</p> <p>There is a need for action on policy level, as well as at technical infrastructure, such as Cluster governance, MoU, and legally binding agreements.</p>
Links to materials	Slides: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6448021
	Video recording: https://youtu.be/8rDdMVFm6O0

PARALLEL SESSION 2: MULTILINGUISM: A TOUR OF NEW SSH RESEARCH ENABLERS

Organisers	Monica Monachini and Francesca Frontini, CNR, CLARIN
Main takeaways and considerations for the future	<p>SSHOC has assured that the services/tools produced would be sustainable and provided a platform for collaboration between partners supporting with their expertise (e.g. dissemination)</p> <p>End users' and other related groups (e.g., NGOs, policy related communities) feedback and advice is deemed useful and needed</p> <p>Common challenge identified is the sustainability of the results, mainly by maintaining and expanding the user's base.</p> <p>Open points for the future:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Adding extra tools to the researchers' toolbox Ensuring quality of and harmonisation in the tools provided
Links to materials	Slides: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6448053
	Video recording: https://youtu.be/3G9Fq6MzriA

PARALLEL SESSION 3: IN PRACTICE: INTEROPERABILITY AND DATA MANAGEMENT IN SSH

Organisers	Emiliano Degl'Innocenti and Carmen Di Meo, CNR, E-RIHS
Main takeaways and considerations for the future	<p>Clusters such as SSHOC can provide awareness of solutions and problems to the fragmented ecosystem of cultural heritage science and can bring the right stakeholders to the discussion about the issues. Interoperability is a process where the aim is to move from a sea of data islands to an organised information data graph.</p>

	<p>The RESTORE platform enables smart access to digital heritage and memory, building from the heterogeneity of formats and lack of semantic interoperability. Latest improvement is visualisation – possibility of virtual exhibitions on the platform.</p> <p>Starting point of the Aïoli, web service for the reality-based 3D annotation, was the idea of many stakeholders describing the object for multidisciplinary observation. Many technical innovations were included: 3D mapping and annotation process, morphology-based data structuring approach, many sharing and visibility options.</p> <p>New recommendations on data citation were adapted for specific needs of SSH, based on the Force11 data citation principles, to support findability of datasets. The data citation prototype also support machine interoperability and actionability of citations by linking information from different sources, bringing the community closer to a fully operational</p> <p>Web Panel Sample Service, a web application for high-quality cross-national probability-based online panels, is a tool for SSH and beyond, removing linguistic barriers. EOSC and SSH Open Marketplace have already contributed to its visibility and uptake.</p> <p>Archive in Box adapts Dataverse, an open repository software, for SSH needs, offering simple implementation to institutions with limited technical capacities. The solution can be adapted to specific communities, allows for specific metadata schemes, support interoperability with external vocabularies, and will contribute to breaking down the silos through a network of linked data repositories in the future.</p> <p>The focus of making tools interoperable is not to have researchers being forced to use tools but to motivate them to use the tools.</p>
Links to materials	<p>Slides: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6448217</p> <p>Video recording: https://youtu.be/li9zkVqTlxw</p>

PARALLEL SESSION 4: SSHOC PRACTICAL PROMPTS FOR DATA AND RESEARCH

Organiser and moderator	Daniela Negoita (Tilburg University)
Main takeaways and considerations for the future	<p>ESS ERIC is registered as a service on EOSC. ESS 9 round is the first on the new platform and will be available only at the platform.</p> <p>Adding new data (SHARE ERIC) is always complex. The process needs to be reviewed and adapted to new circumstances .</p>

	<p>surveycodings.org is an online tool for the coding/measurement of crucial social science variables, available in different languages for multiple countries and beneficial for public opinion surveys, social science projects, data archives, researchers, and any other interested parties.</p> <p>The Multilingual Corpus of Survey Questionnaires (MCSQ) is the first publicly available corpus of survey questionnaires and a powerful instrument for the further development of best practice in design of source questionnaire and questionnaire translation methodologies.</p>
Links to materials	Slides: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6448183
	Video recording: https://youtu.be/5SjGCvtMfo

QUIZZ & NETWORKING DRINKS WITH OUR ON- AND OFFLINE GUESTS

Organisers	Judith Wehmeyer (GESIS), Marieke Willems (Trust-IT), Irena Vipavc Brvar (UL/FDV-ADP)
Moderator	Irena Vipavc Brvar (UL/FDV-ADP)
Materials	See Appendix 2 for Quiz questions and participants' responses.

OPENING PLENARY: BREAKING DOWN SILOS ON THE ROAD TO THE SSH OPEN CLUSTER

Organisers	Rosie Allison and Astrid Verheusen (LIBER)
Main takeaways and considerations for the future	<p>The silos metaphor is useful, but suggests too much uniformity, masks substandard practices, and overshadows the actual problems of the research communities. Silos allow the data communities to work properly in their specialisations. Both specialised and cross-specialisation research are needed. We must look for ways to connect them, but not at a cost of one or another.</p> <p>A Memorandum of Understanding, signed by the SSHOC consortium, will strengthen internal connections, support common interests, and represent the community. It will also support the incoming communities, share visibility and branding, advocate for the needs of the community, act as a single point of contact, and foster impact of SSH research.</p> <p>The transition from SSH Open Cloud to the SSH Open Cluster means a new model of future collaboration: structural collaboration with other RI clusters based on joint thematic agendas and preparing an SSH-wide RI agenda. The partnership must promote the relevance of SSH for public policy, longitudinal value of research data, and organise a strong program for educating and training next generations.</p>

	The SSH Open Marketplace will be sustained by an agreement of CESSDA, CLARIN and DARIAH that will provide the resources needed for maintaining and further development. User community will contribute or enrich the content, while the editorial board will oversee day-to-day operations.
Links to materials	Slides: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6448367
	Video recording: NA

PARALLEL SESSION 5: DEEP DIVE: TRAINING RESOURCES FAIRIFICATION, COMMUNITY AND FUTURE OPPORTUNITIES

Organisers	Tatsiana Yankelevich, LIBER, and Ricarda Braukmann, DANS KNAW
Main takeaways and considerations for the future	<p>The RDA focus group on the minimal metadata of training resources addresses specific challenges on the findability of learning resources and on relevant descriptors. The main goals of the focus group has been to identify a minimal set of metadata descriptors to be recommended as important elements for resource users, but also as a core set that could be adopted by learning resource creators and service providers. The recommendations¹³ for this minimal set of metadata with 14 identified elements for descriptors of training materials, aim at reducing duplication & identify gaps among existing and prospective learning resource service providers.</p> <p>The community-led approach followed by the presented initiatives, such as the RDA focus group and the SSHOC project, brought together different backgrounds, viewpoints and levels of expertise that were invaluable for the work progress, but also in the building and validation of SSH training standards and tools. Feedback loops from the extended SSH training community also ensured that real needs are met and challenges are addressed in a pragmatic way. The SSH Training Discovery Toolkit currently contains 100 sources and 259 examples on reusable training resources.</p> <p>Following an analysis of the CLARIN training resources under the SSH Training Discovery Toolkit, several conclusions came up in terms of future development, quality, reusability and FAIRification of resources. CLARIN has launched a Call for Submissions “Teaching with CLARIN”.¹⁴ The submissions will be assessed across: 1. Accessibility and level of reusability in the context of open science / open training; 2. Adaptability and modularity; 3. Clarity, comprehensibility and</p>

¹³ Recommendations, <https://www.rd-alliance.org/group/education-and-training-handling-research-data-ig/outcomes/recommendations-minimal-metadata-set>. Last accessed 20/04/2022

¹⁴ Call for submissions, <https://www.clarin.eu/content/call-submissions-teaching-clarin-call>. Last accessed 20/04/2022

	<p>readability; 4. Content and technical accuracy; 5. Appropriateness and relevance for the CLARIN communities. These training materials will be included in the SSH Training Discovery Toolkit.</p> <p>The implementation of FAIR training materials in the EOSC Future project uses the RDA minimum metadata for training resources. It is approached in four pilot cases, adapted with criteria varying for aggregated pre-existing materials vs new directly added materials. It follows a pragmatic approach to ensure inclusivity and puts significant effort in ensuring FAIR by design. At the same time, OpenAIRE is about to launch OpenPlato, an LMS and catalogue. OpenAIRE has largely adopted the RDA minimum metadata set too and are opening it up to community end-users for free use, as well as to providers from OpenAIRE members, and as yet not fully defined third parties.</p> <p>CESSDA's path in making training materials FAIR focuses on discovering and using data, managing research data, and preserving data and using CESSDA's tools and services. Further work is to take place with regards to defining new workflows for organisers, publishers and editors, training events and sprints for updating metadata information, strategies for publishing and versioning Train-the-Trainer materials, as well as collaboration on controlled vocabularies.</p> <p>Considerations for the future:</p> <p>FAIRification of training materials needs to be thought about at the beginning of the process, as well as sustainability aspects of training resources and training support tools;</p> <p>Extended metadata and documentation are vital in filling in gaps and possible limitations of the RDA minimal metadata set.</p> <p>A community-led, bottom-up approach and enough effort in developing tools, but also in the curation of training materials is key. A good quality catalogue is hard work and needs community effort/feedback and community standards. The curation needs to be done by a team of people coming from the community with different kinds of expertise.</p> <p>An agreement on controlled vocabularies to be used at the level of the relevant research infrastructures would be very useful.</p> <p>Harmonization, common standards and community-led effort are important for increasing usability and ensuring sustainability.</p>
Links to materials	<p>Slides: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6448440</p> <p>Video recording: NA</p>

PARALLEL SESSION 6: HOW TO BECOME A SSHOCINGLY TRUSTWORTHY ENVIRONMENT FOR SSH DATA

Organiser and moderator	Mari Kleemola (Tampere University)
Main takeaways and considerations for the future	<p>Without SSHOC support, the process of applying to get certification would be much more complicated and longer. These applications are usually time consuming and require the involvement of different experts in the repository. It's a challenge to find a certification solution that works for all repositories. Note that Trusted Digital Repository (TDR) certification improves repository practices (Henri Ala-Lahti, Tampere University).</p> <p>SSHOC Code of Conduct will facilitate SSH repositories to reach GDPR. This will require a monitoring body as well. A SSH code of conduct will benefit EOSC (Marianne Høgetveit Myhren, SIKT).</p> <p>We need to train people on remote safe desktop systems. We created an “international secure data facility professionals network” to help people and small teams in having secure connections thanks to our remote connection. Two outputs should be mentioned: D5.20 Training Materials of workshops for secure data facility professionals (materials are available online), and D5.12 International Secure Data Facility Professionals Network (first meeting 30 March, 2022). Aim of the network is to provide support & knowledge exchange (Deborah Wiltshire, GESIS).</p> <p>Opening access to research data in the archaeology domain - digital data is fragile, as well as archeological data. A report on challenges to access archeological FAIR Data and solutions to overcome them is available. Overall, undertaking the FAIR audit and research was very useful for the Archaeology Data Service (Holly Wright, University of York).</p>
Links to materials	<p>Slides: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6448438</p> <p>Video recording: NA</p>

SSHOC'N TELL USER STORIES PARADE

Organiser and moderator	Marieke Willems, Trust-IT, Irena Vipavc Brvar, CESSDA
See section 3.4 for summary.	
Links to materials	Video recording: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=RkJYqhttpvc

CLOSING PLENARY: AFTERSHOC: SYNERGIES ALONG THE JOURNEY TO EOSC AND A VIEW INTO THE FUTURE

Organiser and moderator	Ivana Ilijašić Veršić, CESSDA
Main takeaways and considerations for the future	<p>Collaboration of ESFRI clusters is essential for funding, addressing researchers by domain rather than fragmented RIs, data FAIRification, promotion of open science, and FAIR compliance.</p> <p>To reach out to end-user communities, systematic training and awareness raising from the ground up is needed, starting already at the level of MA. EOSC resources can support this engagement at national level.</p> <p>Clusters and EOSC collaborate and divide labour to understand the needs of the next generation of researchers and support them.</p>
Links to materials	<p>Slides: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6448575</p> <p>Video recording:</p>

3.4 SSHOC'n Tell Challenge

Parallel to the conference, European researchers were invited to test the SSHOC tools and present their user experience in the SSHOC'n Tell Challenge. The timeline of the activity was as follows:

- April 1 at 12:00: Info session pre challenge
- April 6 at 9:00: Challenge Launch¹⁵
Registered participants attend a kick-off session in which the logistics of how to participate are explained (KreativDistrikt), the expected content of the milestones is outlined and the mentors introduced.
- April 6 from 9:30 to 12:30: Teams define their idea and work on Milestone 1
- April 6 at 12:30: Submission deadline for Milestone 1
- April 7 from 9:00 to 12:30: Teams work on Milestone 2
- April 7 at 12:30: Submission deadline for Milestone 2
- April 7 12:30 to 13:30: Evaluation period (judges)
- April 7 13:30-14:30: SSHOC'n Tell User Stories Parade and Award Ceremony, where teams pitch their ideas and outputs.

A total of **32 participants** registered for the Challenge. From that number, **6 teams were created** with 9 participants representing **4 different countries** (Netherlands, Germany, France, Spain). The Challenge

¹⁵ Video recording of the session, <https://youtu.be/pr-B42WPpK8>. Last accessed 20/04/2022

was successful in producing 6 user stories from a diversely spread group of researchers from across Europe.

The winning team was the Complutense Madrid team (Adrián Menéndez de la Cuesta González, María Robles Pérez, Amelia Sanz) with an average score of 7.08 awarded by the judges. Their user story discussed the user-friendliness of the SSHOC Open Marketplace, and gave tips and bottom-up strategies that could help disseminate the use of this tool, e.g., offering the Marketplace in several languages, allowing filtering based on how difficult the tools are to use, and generally aligning the design of the Marketplace with all its intended audiences. This user story offered a valuable insight into the usability of the SSHOC Marketplace for the everyday user and offers valuable advice that will be taken into consideration in the future upkeep of the tool. A full description of the winning team’s user story can be read in their submitted Milestone.¹⁶

A full report of the SSHOC’n Tell Challenge, including the full marking criteria used by the judges and links to all submitted user stories (developed by KreativDistrikt), can be read in Appendix 3.

¹⁶ Menéndez de la Cuesta, Adrián, Robles, María, & Sanz, Amelia. (2022, April 20). SSHOC'n Tell Challenge - Localizando herramientas/Localizing tools. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6473052>

4. Results

4.1 Participants

A total of 290 participants joined the conference over the two days. Within that figure, the breakdown of online and in-person participants was as follows:

Table 1. Breakdown of online and in-person participants

In person	90*
Online	200

*Of which 78 joined for both days, 9 attended only Day 1 and 3 attended only on Day 2.

Upon registration, participants were asked to state which stakeholder category they belonged to, based on the defined stakeholder categories.¹⁷ The breakdown was as follows:

Table 2. Breakdown of participants by stakeholder categories

Stakeholder Category	Participants
Civil Society and Citizen Scientists	2
Policy Making Organisations	8
Private Sector and Industry Players	17
Research & e-Infrastructure and EOSC thematic clusters	72
Research Funding Organisations	8
Research Libraries & Archives	71
Researchers	64
Universities & Research Performing Organisations	48
Total	290

In terms of participant reach, the conference was very successful in attracting a geographically varied group of participants from 37 different countries. The full breakdown of participants per country is outlined below:

Table 3: Breakdown of participants by country of origin

Country	Participants
Algeria	1
Australia	1
Austria	11
Belgium	14
Bulgaria	1
China	1

¹⁷ Identified in *D2.1 SSHOC Overall Communication and Outreach Plan* (Schwabe et al. 2019) and *D6.1 SSHOC Community Engagement Strategy* (Torma et al. 2019b).

Croatia	9
Czech Republic	5
Denmark	6
Finland	7
France	23
Germany	31
Greece	6
India	4
Ireland	4
Italy	34
Latvia	2
Lithuania	1
Luxembourg	1
Mexico	1
Morocco	1
Netherlands	49
Norway	10
Peru	1
Poland	7
Portugal	2
Romania	3
Serbia	4
Slovakia	1
Slovenia	4
Spain	6
Sweden	3
Switzerland	5
Turkey	2
United Kingdom	26
United States	2
Zambia	1
Total	290

Participant roles were also registered and are illustrated in the Wordcloud below, with the predominant participant roles being ‘researcher’, ‘project manager’ and ‘librarian’:

SSHOC Final Conference are given equal technical support, to ensure that all topics have an equal chance of attracting and maintaining online participants.

Figure 2: Livestream analytics for the Einstein room

Figure 3: Livestream analytics for the Baekeland room

4.2 Participant feedback

To evaluate further the success, and points of improvement, for the SSHOC Final Conference, a post-event survey was sent out to all participants. A total of 40 participants completed the survey, of which 17 attended online and 23 attended in-person. The following diagrams show the results of the participant survey.

Scale ranges from 1 - poor, to 5 - excellent.

Where did you learn about the conference?

40 responses

- SSHOC website
- Social Media
- Colleagues
- Mailing list or newsletter
- Event
- project partner
- EOSC website
- within LIBER organisation
- SSHOC project
- I've worked in the project
- I was part of the organisation
- Statt in SSHOC
- EOSC Association website

How well organised was the conference in terms of time management, length, and venue?

40 responses

Scale ranges from 1 - poorly organised, to 5 - excellently organised.

Scale ranges from 1 - much less than expected, to 5 - greatly exceeded expectations.

Feedback was also collected on what the participants liked the most, what they missed, and what was their takeaway message. The responses are added as an appendix (see Appendix 4).

4.3 Lessons learned

The hybrid format presented both one of the main challenges for the organisation and a great added value for accessibility and visibility of the conference. In terms of public health concerns, the conference coincided with a relatively relaxed period in which the number of COVID-19 cases in Europe was comparably low and the travelling restrictions in most EU countries were relaxed. This meant that many members of the community felt more comfortable travelling and participating in group activities. However, the ratio of in-person and online participants was still strongly in favour of the latter. The organisation had considered the needs of the groups from the start: sufficient breaks were planned; the agenda was adjusted so that the days were neither too long for those joining online nor too meagre for those who travelled to the premises; both groups were able to join the same informal networking activity.

For those who were not able to travel for any reason, the hybrid format allowed them to join the sessions they were interested in, follow the debate, and add comments or ask questions via the Bluepoint conference tool. Speakers were also able to present and join the discussion panels online. A downside of the chosen conference tool was that the participants were not able to speak out themselves, but could only ask questions or contribute to the debate through an intermediary - the so-called chat checker. The participants' comments in the post-event survey demonstrate that this was well received by some, while others had expected more. On the other hand, the attendance and engagement on the premises exceeded expectations, and the in-person participants were impressed by the potential of the hybrid sessions.

A truly hybrid event where online participants would be able to participate just as actively and timely as the in-person participants is technically possible, but requires a higher financial investment, a significantly stronger team at the premises, as well as careful management of any online conference tool. For the SSHOC conference, this would require at least one additional member of the support team onsite, per session. The organisation of hybrid events in general necessitates a great deal more effort and financial resources than either online- or in person-only events. The type of hybridity that was offered in the SSHOC final conference was, however, more than sufficient to successfully showcase the outcomes of the project.

5. Conclusion

The final conference was a lively meeting that succeeded in showcasing the results and discussing the impact of the project with a varied community of participants both online and face-to-face. A good range of SSHOC stakeholders attended the event and the geographical reach, thanks largely to the hybrid format allowing participants to attend online, was also satisfactory. Thus, it can be optimistically concluded that the conference succeeding in its aim of showcasing project achievements by engaging with a broad range of SSHOC stakeholders and European research initiatives.

Although the hybrid format caused some organisational difficulties, the feedback from participants was that they highly appreciated the ability to attend both in-person and online. For the online audience, barriers such as the continued difficulties with travelling during the current period were removed allowing everyone equal access to conference content. For in-person participants the sense of SSH community was strengthened through the numerous opportunities for networking. Despite the challenges, the hybrid format was successful in catering to a broad range of SSHOC stakeholder needs and ultimately engaging a larger proportion of participants than a fully in-person conference would have allowed.

The conclusion of the conference was to demonstrate how the collaborations and accomplishments of the past years will continue to grow and develop within the framework of the SSH Open Cluster. The organising committee was influential in guiding the content of each session to ensure that they did not purely describe and reiterate project results, but looked to the future of how SSHOC tools, communities and collaborations can benefit and support the next generation of researchers. The hope of the organisers is that the final conference can be considered not only as a conclusion of the project, but as a start of new endeavours.

6. References

- Darja Fišer, Erzsébet Tóth-Czifra, Judith Wehmeyer, Veronika Keck, Ellen Leenarts, Ricarda Braukmann, Tatsiana Yankelevich, & Cristina Magder. (2021). D6.12 Report on the SSHOC train-the-trainer bootcamps. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5734301>
- Gotz, Andy, Petzold, Andreas, Asmi, Ari, Blomberg, Niklas, Lamanna, Giovanni, & Dekker, Ron. (2020). ESFRI cluster projects - Position papers on expectations and planned contributions to the EOSC. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3675081>
- Ana Inkret, Rosie Allison, & Irena Vipavc Brvar. (2021). D6.3 Final report on the outcome of the awareness raising workshops. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5913518>
- Ana Inkret & Irena Vipavc Brvar. (2022). D6.4 Report on the awareness webinars.
- Menéndez de la Cuesta, Adrián, Robles, María, & Sanz, Amelia. (2022, April 20). SSHOC'n Tell Challenge - Localizando herramientas/Localizing tools. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6473052>
- Martina Torma, Vasso Kalaitzi, Elly Dijk, Marion Wittenberg, Marieke Willems, Darja Fiser, Kristina Pahor de Maiti, Matej Durco, & Irena Vipavc Brvar. (2019a). SSHOC D6.2 Building Expertise Strategy (v1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4558294>
- Torma, Martina, Kalaitzi, Vasso, Vipavc Brvar, Irena, Fišer, Darja, Pahor de Maiti, Kristina, Petitfils, Clara, Durco, Matej, Grant, Friedel, & Willems, Marieke. (2019b). SSHOC D6.1 Community Engagement Strategy (v1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3592244>
- Annika Schwabe, Julian Ausserhofer, Leonardo Marino, Marieke Willems, Vasso Kalaitzi, Irena Vipavc Brvar, Eleonor Smith, & Silvana Muscella. (2019). SSHOC D2.1 Overall Communication and Outreach Plan (approved 18 nov 2019) (v1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3595936>
- SSHOC. (2022). SSHOC Legacy booklet. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6394462>

List of Figures

[Figure 1: Word cloud of participants' roles in their organisations](#)

[Figure 2: Livestream analytics for the Einstein room](#)

[Figure 3: Livestream analytics for the Baekeland room](#)

List of Tables

[Table 1. Breakdown of online and in-person participants](#)

[Table 2. Breakdown of participants by stakeholder categories](#)

[Table 3: Breakdown of participants by country of origin](#)

Appendix 1 - SSHOC'n Tell Challenge Starter Kit

Welcome to the SSHOC'n Tell Challenge!

We're thrilled to have you on board the **SSHOC'n Tell Challenge** and can't wait to share this experience with you. During the challenge, you will work side by side with a **SHOCC'n Tell Mentor**. In addition, the whole challenge's **Coordination Team** will be there to provide you with resources, guidance and support to guide you through the whole experience. For questions at any point during the overall activities planned before and during the challenge, you can contact us at info@kreativdistrikt.com

INDEX

[SSHOC'n Tell CHALLENGE's goal](#)

[TOPICS & CHALLENGES](#)

- [TOPIC 1 - Virtual Collection Registry and Switchboard](#)
- [TOPIC 2 - SSH Open Marketplace](#)
- [TOPIC 3- TRAINING](#)
- [TOPIC 4 - WILDCARD - Advance your own research](#)

[AGENDA OF THE SSHOC'n Tell CHALLENGE](#)

[HOW TO CORRECTLY PARTICIPATE IN THE CHALLENGE](#)

[MILESTONES](#)

- [Milestone 1 // Page Summary](#)
- [Milestone 2 // Presentation](#)

[HOW TO SUBMIT THE MILESTONES](#)

[HOW TO INTERACT WITH THE MENTORS](#)

[CHALLENGE RESOURCES](#)

[JUDGING PROCESS](#)

[WINNERS ANNOUNCEMENT](#)

[CHALLENGE SUPPORT](#)

SSHOC'n Tell CHALLENGE'S GOAL

The SSHOC'n Tell Challenge is an open invitation to Social Science and Humanities (SSH) researchers, data experts, trainers, and Research Infrastructure professionals to participate in a two-day event where teams will create working cases within different challenges! You will be challenged to develop user stories with the SSHOC tools for your research, training or research Infrastructure trying out one or more of them. SSHOC, "Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud", has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 project call H2020-INFRAEOSC-04-2018, grant agreement #823782. [Privacy Policy and Terms of Use](#)

TOPICS & CHALLENGES

As a participant of the SSHOC'n Tell Challenge, you will be challenged to develop a user story to address one of the following Topics. Each topic has **challenge(s)** in it:

TOPIC 1 – Virtual Collection Registry and Switchboard

From January 2019 to April 2022 SSHOC transformed the current social sciences & humanities data landscape with its disciplinary silos and separate facilities into an integrated, cloud-based network of interconnected data infrastructures.

To promote synergies and open science initiatives between disciplines, and accelerate interdisciplinary research and collaboration, these data infrastructures are supported by the tools and training which allow scholars and researchers to access, process, analyse, enrich and compare data across the boundaries of individual repositories or institutions.

This session will follow this approach and address two established individual services – the Switchboard and the Virtual Collection Registry – with a provenance from a specific data domain (CLARIN, language related research data) and investigate adoption scenarios for other data domains. Both tools are per concept suitable to be applied in other domains such as the social sciences but also beyond. Our aim in this session is therefore to investigate such adoptions and describe them in user stories."

The SSHOC'n Tell Challenges are defined to try out these tools and share your user story.

Mentors: Stefan Buddenbohm (UGOE, DARIAH), Willem Elbers (CLARIN), Emanuel Dimă (EKUT, CLARIN)

Challenges in this topic:

**A) How might we adapt the Virtual Collection Registry for other research domains?
What features would be necessary to scale up the use of the VCR?**

The challenge is to explore the usability of the Virtual Collection Registry (VCR) in your research domain. So far the audience and users of the VCR are often affiliated with the CLARIN research infrastructure. But the VCR may be of use for the social sciences or other humanities domains or even other disciplines.

Your challenge is to experiment with the VCR against your individual research background. How can the VCR be applied with your discipline-specific research and publication practices? What would be necessary with regard to interoperability of virtual collections (and virtual collection records)? Does the VCR miss certain features in its current state? What is necessary – in your opinion – to allow an uptake of the VCR in your community? Specifically of interest are your thoughts and proposals concerning the sharing and collaboration aspects when it comes to research data.

What is the VCR about? The VCR is a tool for creating virtual collections. A virtual collection may be a bibliography of sources when writing a journal article. But a virtual collection may be much more and can include references to the research data your journal article is based on. Or the applied services and methods may be references in the virtual collection. The bottom line is that the VCR allows you to create reference to a broad variety of sources and data and the session your challenge is to explore such scenarios.

Available in SSHOC relevant to this challenge:

- Web services: <https://www.clarin.eu/content/virtual-collections>

Examples of potential ideas:

- Create a VC from different repositories where the VCR was integrated: ARCHE, VLO, SND, and also somewhere it was not integrated eg. TextGrid.
- Discuss the VC concept and ask for feedback on wrt ease of use of VCR and the functionality of the tools offered for VCR eg. WeblichtBatch and CMDIexplorer.
- The Switchboard papers as an example for a VC:
<https://collections.clarin.eu/details/1061?2&backPage=0>
- The Trobriand Way of Islanders' speaking:
<https://collections.clarin.eu/details/1000?3&backPage=0>

All the above resources can also be found in the SSHOC booklet [downloadable here](#).

B) What tools and services might be added to the Switchboard to make it useful for other research domains? Where should the Switchboard be visible/accessible in your research data domain?

Your challenge is to test the Switchboard and explore use scenarios for the service in your individual research domain. Such use scenarios should consider the interoperability of the Switchboard with your research data. This part of the challenge is directed at extending the current tool inventory of the Switchboard. Use scenarios can also include relevant services where collections of research data are stored for re-use, e.g. repositories.

What is the Switchboard about? The Switchboard allows researchers to find and explore tools and services for their individual research data. Depending on the technical metadata of an individual research data record – for instance a text stored in a repository – the Switchboard may suggest tools for text analysis or text mining. Currently the Switchboard offers a range of over 50 tools and services which can be explored by uploading an exemplary dataset to the service. Beyond this, the Switchboard is also integrated in repositories, where the user is able to pick and send an exemplary dataset to the Switchboard in a very convenient way.

Available in SSHOC relevant to this challenge:

- Datasets: <https://textgridrep.org/browse/tbz8.0>
- Tools: <https://switchboard.clarin.eu/tools>
- Web services <https://switchboard.clarin.eu/>

Examples of potential ideas:

- TextGrid repository as example for the integration of the Switchboard in a discipline specific repository: <https://textgridrep.org/browse/tbz8.0>
- discuss the Switchboard, asking adopters/researchers that have been primed already with some documentation, to provide some feedback on how they usually work with data resources (text, xml, ? files) and ask them to try the switchboard to invoke some services to process these. NLP /Weblicht batch, ...
Execute Switchboard from CLARIN VLO, TextGrid,

All the above resources can also be found in the SSHOC booklet [downloadable here](#).

TOPIC 2 – SSH Open Marketplace

How might we use SSHOC tools to perform SSH and interdisciplinary research?

The Social Sciences and Humanities Open Marketplace, built as part of the Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud project (SSHOC), is a discovery portal that pools and contextualizes resources for Social Sciences and Humanities research communities: tools, services, training materials, datasets, publications, and workflows. The Marketplace highlights and showcases solutions and research practices for every step of the SSH research data life cycle.

The SSH Open Marketplace is:

- a discovery portal, to foster serendipity in digital methods
- an aggregator of useful and well-curated resources
- a catalog, contextualising resources
- an entry point in the EOSC for the Social Sciences and Humanities researchers

The SSHOC'n Tell Challenges are defined to try out the SSH Open Marketplace and share your user story.

Challenges in this topic:

Challenge 2A – Make the tools and resources of your community visible

How might we use the SSH Open Marketplace to reference tools, services, or other resources used in a given research community?

Your challenge is to look for/search for the tools and resources you've used to work with and enrich their records in the SSH Open Marketplace. By doing so, you help others to discover and reuse them.

Available in SSHOC relevant to this challenge:

- SSH Open Marketplace: <https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu>
- Create and enrich an individual item in the SSH Open Marketplace, guidelines: <https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/contribute/enrich-an-individual-item> (and <https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/contribute/create-an-individual-item>)

Examples of potential ideas:

- Example 1: Gephi entry in the SSH Open Marketplace – <https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/tool-or-service/87wJWo> – includes comprehensive metadata and relations to other items
- Example 2: TaDiRAH Taxonomy of Digital Research Activities in the Humanities – <https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/tool-or-service/mLb9Pk>
- Example 3: WageIndicator Collective Agreements Database Dataset with Full Texts and Selected Clauses Dataset – <https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/dataset/jveQkU>

All the above resources can also be found in the SSHOC booklet [downloadable here](#).

Challenge 2B – Create a living memory of what the best research practices in your given community should be

How might we use the SSH Open Marketplace:

- to make your research project align with the best practices in your community?
- to get peer review and visibility?
- to share a project in another form than the usual blog / article (a new way to disseminate your work)?

Your challenge is to create a workflow in/using the SSH Open Marketplace. As a sequence of steps describing how to perform a task within the research data lifecycle, a SSH Open Marketplace workflow is an innovative way to make digital methods accessible and reusable for other researchers wishing to carry out a similar project but unfamiliar with the recommended tools or formats to use.

Available in SSHOC relevant to this challenge:

- *Tutorial – How to create a workflow in the SSH Open Marketplace?*
<https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/workflow/hmGpmv>
- *Presentation – Sharing digital tools in context: the SSH Open Marketplace –*
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5535742>

Examples of potential ideas:

- Example 1: Create a dictionary in TEI
<https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/workflow/4qFarh>

- Example 2: Collaborative Digital Edition of a Musical Corpus
<https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/workflow/bKefY4>

All the above resources can also be found in the SSHOC booklet [downloadable here](#).

Challenge 2C – Reuse the SSH Open Marketplace data using the Application Programming Interface (API)

This challenge may require some coding skills and a familiarity with the use of REST API .

How might we reuse the Marketplace data to select and/or visualise its content or part of its content relevant to a specific SSH community? Thanks to the SSH Open Marketplace API, it is possible to search and retrieve detailed information on all items.

Your challenge is to explore the Marketplace data and metadata via the API. After identifying a subset of interest for you or a given research community (disciplinary, geographically...), you will query the SSH Open Marketplace API, and build on the results to provide creative ways to process or visualise the SSH Open Marketplace data.

Available in SSHOC relevant to this challenge:

- API documentation –
<https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/about/implementation>
- SSH Open Marketplace Python library –
<https://gitlab.gwdg.de/sshoc/marketplace-curation>

Examples of potential ideas:

- Example 1: visualising data and metadata of the SSH Open Marketplace

All the above resources can also be found in the SSHOC booklet [downloadable here](#).

TOPIC 3- TRAINING

As we built the SSH area of the European Open Science Cloud, a key focus for SSHOC was providing training, advice, and educational resources for producers, users, and curators of Social Sciences and Humanities data. In the training challenges we invite you to try out training resources developed in SSHOC and tell us about your experience.

Challenges in this topic:

CHALLENGE 3A – I am preparing a training session on Open Science and looking for materials to reuse. Can I find these materials using the Training Discovery Toolkit (TDT)– and how can I reuse them?

As a resource for researchers, service providers, data stewards, and trainers in the Social Sciences and Humanities, the SSH Training Discovery Toolkit provides an inventory of educational materials covering topics including Research data management, FAIR data, Open Science, Programming and Didactics.

How might we use the SSH Training Discovery Toolkit (TDT) to find reusable training resources? The SSHOC'n Tell Challenges are defined to try out the TDT and share your user story.

This challenge will only take you 30 min. Your story is what we're looking for. This challenge takes place only on Day 1 but you're free to submit Milestone 2 before day 2's deadline!

Available in SSHOC relevant to this challenge:

- Training Discovery Toolkit: <https://training-toolkit.sshopencloud.eu>
- Presentation of the Toolkit and "game" use case: Day 2 SSHOC Discovery

Toolkit.pptx [DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4813115>]

Examples:

- As a researcher/ trainer in the Social Sciences and Humanities I

feel that there is a lack of training materials for _____.

- Using the TDT I discovered _____ .

CHALLENGE 3B – I am working on a training session, but am struggling to make it interactive. How can I use the Training Discovery Toolkit to achieve this goal?

As a resource for researchers, service providers, data stewards, and trainers in the Social Sciences and Humanities, the SSH Training Discovery Toolkit provides an inventory of educational materials covering topics including Research data management, FAIR data, Open Science, Programming and Didactics.

How might we use the SSH Training Discovery Toolkit (TDT) to find reusable training resources? The SSHOC'n Tell Challenges are defined to try out the TDT and share your user story.

This challenge will only take you 30 min. Your story is what we're looking for. This challenge takes place only on Day 1 but you're free to submit Milestone 2 before day 2's deadline!

Available in SSHOC relevant to this challenge:

- Training Discovery Toolkit: <https://training-toolkit.sshopencloud.eu>
- Presentation of the Toolkit and "game" use case: Day 2 SSHOC Discovery

Toolkit.pptx [DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4813115>]

Examples:

- As someone giving a lecture or training, I want to find interactive games in order to make my teaching more interactive.
- As a researcher in the Social Sciences and Humanities I feel that there is a lack of training materials for _____.
- Using the TDT I discovered _____.

CHALLENGE 3C – Play the SSHOC League of Data and learn how to Archive and Publish your research data.

The SSHOC League of Data (SSHOC LoD) is a pilot gamification of the CESSDA Data Management Expert Guide. The game supports and motivates researchers to publish their research data, by providing guidance for the publishing process. With respect to the preparation of research data for its publication, LoD shall convert an otherwise strenuous and opaque process, including lots of internet search and the study of bulky standards, into an exciting and joyful adventure which provides unknown opportunities

and possibilities. The SSHOC LoD is a pilot version for the CESSDA DMEG chapter on Archiving and Publishing.

This challenge will take you less than 30 min. Your story and recommendations for future development are what we're looking for. This challenge takes place only on Day 1 but you're free to submit Milestone 2 before day 2's deadline!

Available in SSHOC relevant to this challenge:

- SSHOC LoD Game: <https://lod.sshopencloud.eu/>

Examples:

- I played the SSHOC League of Data and I learned _____.
- As an early career researcher looking to learn in a fun way about Archiving and Publishing my data I feel that I miss information about _____.
- Using the SSHOC LoD I discovered _____.

TOPIC 4 – WILDCARD – Advance your own research

From January 2019 to April 2022 SSHOC transformed the current social sciences and humanities data landscape with its disciplinary silos and separate facilities into an integrated, cloud-based network of interconnected data infrastructures.

To promote synergies and open science initiatives between disciplines, and accelerate interdisciplinary research and collaboration, these data infrastructures are supported by the tools and training which allow scholars and researchers to access, process, analyse, enrich and compare data across the boundaries of individual repositories or institutions.

The SSHOC'n Tell Challenges are defined to try out these tools and share your user story.

How might we use SSHOC tools for our research?

Challenge 4 – How would you use any of the available SSHOC tools to advance your own research? To answer your research question?

Available in SSHOC relevant to this challenge:

- SSH open Marketplace: <https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu>
- Tools specifically developed by SSHOC:
<https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/search?order=label&f.source=SSHopencloud+Service+Catalogue>

All the above resources can also be found in the SSHOC booklet [downloadable here](#).

AGENDA OF THE SSHOC'n Tell CHALLENGE

Here's a general overview of the timings & deadlines for milestones of the 2-day challenge:

- ☁ **Info session pre challenge** - 1 April @ 12:00 - CEST
- 🚀 **Challenge starts** - 6 April @ 9:00 - CEST
- 🚩 **Milestone 1 // Page Summary // Submission deadline** - 6 April @ 12:30 - CEST
- 🚩 **Milestone 2 // Presentation // Submission deadline** - 7 April @ 12:30 - CEST
- 📄 **Evaluation** - 7 April @ 12:30 - CEST
- 🎤 **Pitching & Award Live Event** - 7 April @ 13:30 - CEST

An info session Event is planned at **12:00 – CEST on 1 April** During this session, we will explain to you how to leverage the challenge platform and we will provide more information on the challenges and on the mentors that will help you develop your milestones.

You will receive a detailed agenda for the Info session pre-challenge directly on [Eventornado](#), in due time.

HOW TO CORRECTLY PARTICIPATE IN THE CHALLENGE

To correctly participate in the challenge you need, of course, to register first. Upon registration, you will be asked how you would like to participate:

How are you planning to participate?

 I already have a team and I am the Team Leader

 I am joining the team of my Team Leader

 I am applying as an individual and I am looking to join or lead a Team

 I am applying as an individual and I'm planning to participate individually

In case you registered for the option “I am applying as an individual and I am looking to join or lead a Team” please skip to the end of this paragraph.

If you registered selecting 1 of the other 3 options, please read the following guidelines:

GUIDELINES IN CASE REGISTERED SELECTING THE FOLLOWING OPTIONS:

- **I already have a team and I am the Team Leader**
- **I am joining the team of my Team Leader**
- **I am applying as an individual and I'm planning to participate individually**

Once you register, a new “Post idea” button will appear:

You need to Post an Idea in the following 2 cases:

- 1) You're the team leader of your team

2) You're participating individually

Once you click on the "Post idea" green button you will have the chance to create your idea by filling up the idea form:

Please fill the form below 📝

Topic *

Please choose the topic that best fits your idea

Please give your user story a catchy name! *

Describe what caught your eye in this challenge *

...so other participants can team up with you in a group if you plan to work in a team. Otherwise, you're free to fly solo with your user story!

Keywords

Please post relevant keywords for your submission.

This makes it easier for others to find it.

Team *

Please add a team name. Yes, even if you don't have any teammates for now

This is the place for you to name your User Story and your team. If you're participating individually, that's all you have to do to correctly be eligible to participate in the challenge. If you're the Team Leader of your team then the next step would be to invite the other team members. This can be done in the "My Idea" tab that will appear right after you post the idea. Just click on "Invite team member" to invite the other team members through their email address:

Once done, your team members will receive an invitation email from Eventornado. After they accept they will be able to join your team and you will see them under “Members”.

In addition, your private team chat will be automatically created in the Event chat. This is the place for you to communicate and work with your team:

Make sure to keep an eye on the *#announcements* and *#general* channels for important updates about the challenge!

GUIDELINES IN CASE REGISTERED SELECTING THE FOLLOWING OPTION:

- **I am applying as an individual and I am looking to join or lead a Team**

If you don't have a team and you're looking to join one, then you have 2 options to do that.

FIRST OPTION: *#findyourteam* channel

Go straight to the *#findyourteam* channel after registration and write down a description of your background, skills, and preferred challenge so you can meet other participants and form a team together. The steps to create a team are described at the beginning of this paragraph.

SECOND OPTION: Idea's tab

Go straight to the ideas tab and explore the already named user story and teams so you can click on one of them and apply to join:

The screenshot shows the SSHOC Ideas page interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with 'Home', 'Ideas', 'FAQ', and 'Mentors' tabs, and a 'REGISTER' button. Below the navigation is a search bar with the placeholder text 'Type keywords or phrases' and a 'Search' button. There are also two filter dropdowns: 'Random order' and 'Filter based on missing roles'. Underneath, there are 'Topics' tabs for 'Energy Efficiency', 'Transportation', and 'Communities'. The main content area displays a grid of four idea cards, each with a header image, a title, a user profile picture and name, a team name, a list of hashtags, and icons for comments and team members.

Title	User	Team	Hashtags	Comments	Team Members
Recontextualize cross-media bandwidth	Roberto Cuseck	Tipsy lock	#communication #crowdfunding #Open-Source	4	5
Strategize enterprise relationships	Tyson Trollope	Ravishing engineering	#civic engagement #sustainable policy	4	1
Brand integrated networks	Edgar Aronov	Wriggling cost	#compliance #B2B #SaaS	1	4
Morph efficient eyeballs	Eveline Thame	Improper clerk	#crowdsourcing #robotics #Simulation	1	6

Make sure to keep an eye on the *#announcements* and *#general* channels for important updates about the challenge!

MILESTONES

This section outlines the **Milestones** that will be requested from you (or your Team if you're participating individually) at different deadlines. The submission of each milestone is mandatory to be eligible for the final prize.

You're free to organize your work how you wish, but we highly recommend leveraging the Eventornado platform for the video calls and interactions with your team (if you're working in a team) and with your mentor.

Milestone 1 // Page Summary

Due date: 12:30 – CEST on 6 April

Definition: Milestone 1 is a (maximum) 1–page summary that provides a general description of your user story, summarizing its ultimate goal. It should contain the following:

- **What:** tell us about the challenge that you took on and how relevant it is for your daily work in research or research support.
- **Who:** tell us about your SSHOC'n Tell team and who will benefit from your user story.
- **How:** the specific SSHOC tools and/or resources that are used in your story.
- **When:** a short plan for how you will continue to use the SSHOC tool or resources after the SSHOC'n Tell challenge.

Milestone 1 must be produced and submitted using the [template downloadable at this link](#).

Milestone 2 // Presentation

Due date: 12:30 – CEST on 7 April

Definition: Milestone 2 is a (maximum) 7-slide presentation that describes your user story.

Your presentation should address the following points:

- **The User:** Describe yourself, your affiliation and/or research community as the user of the SSHOC service or tool.
- **SSHOC service or tool used:** Explain why and how you applied the SSHOC service and/or tool to deal with this challenge.
- **The Benefits:** Please highlight the benefits you have identified can be obtained by using the SSHOC tool, for example time or cost savings, efficiency, reuse of available data and resources, sharing of expertise, etc.
- **Tips & Tricks:** Do you have any tips & tricks for potential users of the SSHOC tool/service you used? Did you consult any SSHOC training resources or sessions?
- **Picture:** Please provide an image of your team (or yourself in case you're participating individually) that best depicts your SSHOC'n Tell Story.
- **SSHOC User Experience:** How easy was it to familiarize yourself with the use of SSHOC tools and resources?
- **Recommendation:** Anything you would like to recommend for future improvements?

Milestone 2 must be produced and submitted using the [template downloadable at this link](#).

HOW TO SUBMIT THE MILESTONES

The Team Leader of the team or the individual if you're participating individually is responsible for submitting each milestone by its corresponding deadline.

Here's the procedure to do that. First, go to the "My idea" tab and click on "Edit idea":

Once you click on “edit idea” you will be able to see the dedicated upload fields for you to upload your milestones when it’s time:

DELIVERABLE 1 // 1-page summary

Upload here the files for your Deliverable 1 IN PDF FORMAT // THE DOCUMENT MUST BE DELIVERED USING THE TEMPLATE THAT CAN BE DOWNLOADED HERE: www.linktodeliverablefile.com

jpg, jpeg, png, gif, bitmap, tif, pdf, ppt, pptx files with a size less than 20MB

DELIVERABLE 2 // Slide presentation

Upload here the files for your Deliverable 2 // THE DOCUMENT MUST BE DELIVERED USING THE TEMPLATE THAT CAN BE DOWNLOADED HERE: www.linktodeliverablefile.com

jpg, jpeg, png, gif, bitmap, tif, pdf, ppt, pptx files with a size less than 20MB

Make sure to click on “update” when you’re done!

[Update](#)

That's it 🙌

If you encounter problems in submitting your files, please drop a message in the [#organizers_with_teams](#) channel.

HOW TO INTERACT WITH THE MENTORS

We've created different mentor support channels for each challenge, providing you with information about the mentors. To receive support from them you can write them a public chat or a private direct message to them so they can start supporting you!

Here are the channels:

#challenge1_mentorsupport

#challenge2A2B_mentorsupport

#challenge2C_mentorsupport

#challenge3A3B_mentorsupport

#challenge3C_mentorsupport

Home Ideas Judges & Mentors Tools & Resources Post idea Event chat

C # challenge3A3B_mentorsupport

Start of conversation
March 29, 2022

 Michele Erba | Organizer | 3:26 PM
Dear participants,

This chat channel is dedicated exclusively to supporting you with questions related to:

Challenge 3A - I am preparing a training session on Open Science and looking for materials to reuse. Can I find these materials using the Training Discovery Toolkit (TDT) - and how can I reuse them?

and

Challenge 3B - I am working on a training session, but am struggling to make it interactive. How can I use the Training Discovery Toolkit to achieve this goal?

It's the place for you to reach out to **Ellen Leenarts**, the mentor assigned to this challenge, and clear any of your doubts during the 2 days hackathon 🙌

CHALLENGE RESOURCES

A Legacy Booklet is available to provide you with a comprehensive list of resources – including factsheets on the SSHOC tools, pointing to where to access each of these tools on the SSH Open Marketplace and the information available such as **training recordings, videos and background information** that are available in **SSHOC** to try out our tool and tell your user story during the **SSHOC'n Tell Challenge**.

You can download the Booklet [at this link](#) or by clicking on the button below:

DOWNLOAD THE LEGACY BOOKLET

JUDGING PROCESS

A panel of Judges both from the Sponsor and Prize provider will evaluate every project considering the following criteria:

- How effectively was the challenge addressed with the use of SSHOC tools?
- How engaging is the user story told in the Milestones?
- How inspiring are the tips & tricks for potential users?
- How realistic are the recommendations for future improvement?

WINNERS ANNOUNCEMENT

Winners will be announced during the **SSHOC'n Tell Challenge Pitching & Award Live Event** that will be held **at 13:30 – CEST on 7 April**.

You will receive all the details to join directly on Eventornado.

CHALLENGE SUPPORT

At any point during the challenge, you can reach out to the organisers by dropping a message in the [#organizers_with_teams](#) channel. This channel becomes available

only if you're correctly participating in the challenge as explained in the paragraph "HOW TO CORRECTLY PARTICIPATE IN THE CHALLENGE".

You can also send an email to the challenge organisation team at:

info@kreativdistrikt.com

Appendix 2 - Quiz questions and response

**SSHOC Final Conference
Quizz**

06 - 07 Apr 2022

Poll results

slido

Appendix 3 - SSHOC'n Tell Challenge FINAL REPORT

Outreach campaign

 Facebook & IG

- Reach: 90K
- Impressions: 265K
- Link Clicks: 538
- Landing page views: 245
- Comments: 2
- Reactions: 64
- Shares: 6
- Post saves: 31

 Direct Campaign

- Institutions / Universities contacted: 55
- Geo location of institutions: EU
- Targeted profiles: SSH Phd, Researches, Trainers, Data Experts
- Direct emails sent: 12.687
- People contacted directly on LinkedIn: 142

Registrations and participation data

REGISTRATION
Total registrations 32
Total registered Teams 6 (9 participants - 1 with 2 user stories)
Withdrawn / disqualified teams 0 (0 participants)
Total countries represented 4 (Netherlands, Germany, France, Spain)

SSHOCn' Tell mentors

Here to help you!

 Klaus Illmayer Challenge 2C		
 Zach Smith Challenge 3C		

SSHOC'n Tell Topics and Challenges

Challenge 1 - Interoperability & Multilinguality

Challenge 2C - Re-use the SSH Open Marketplace data using the Application Programming Interface (API)

Challenge 2A - Make the tools and resources of your community visible

Challenge 2B - Create a living memory of what the best research practices in your given community should be

Challenge 3A - I am preparing a training session on Open Science and looking for materials to reuse. Can I find these materials using the Training Discovery Toolkit (TDT)- and how can I reuse them?

Challenge 3B - I am working on a training session, but am struggling to make it interactive. How can I use the Training Discovery Toolkit to achieve this goal?

Challenge 3C - Play the SSHOC League of Data and learn how to Archive and Publish your research data.

Challenge 4 - Wildcard

TOPIC 4 - WILDCARD - Advance your own research From January 2019 to April 2022 SSHOC transformed the current social sciences and humanities data landscape with its disciplinary silos and separate fac

The ideas presented

Challenge 1 - Interoperability & Multilinguality

Challenge 1 - Interoperability & Multilinguality

⚡ How to use VCR and Switchboard in teaching and training

Challenge 1 - Interoperability & Multilinguality

🗨️ 1 ❤️ 5

Describe what caught your eye in this challenge

What? Our idea is about applying research tools like the Switchboard, the Virtual Language Observatory (VLO) and the VCR - for teaching scenarios:

Why? We see two main benefits in this idea/challenge, one addressing the students side, the other addressing the tool/services side.

Regarding the students: Learn with and use these tools the students enhance their data discovery and processing skills and also learn how to cite the datasets they use. They gain important contributions to their skillset regarding Research Data Management (RDM), collaborative modes of working (e.g. in the European Research Area) but also addressing the FAIR principles as a per-default mode of doing research today.

Regarding the tool side: a common weak spot of research infrastructures is the missing connection between the developer/provider side and the user community. Often this leads to an unsatisfactory uptake in the community and vice versa to deficits regarding user experience or unsatisfactory integration in the research processes. The intensive use in a teaching environment could address this weak spot.

Additionally this idea/challenge addresses an improved integration and interoperability of the mentioned tools and resources with one another.

👥 Virtual teachers

Members

- **Janna Besamusca NL**
Team lead
- **Nanette Rißler-Pipka**
Other
- **Iulianna van der Lek NL**
leader

The ideas presented

Challenge 2A - Make the tools and resources of your community visible

Challenge 2A - Make the tools and resources of your community visible

⚡ Localizando herramientas/Localizing tools

Challenge 2A - Make the tools and resources of your community visible

2 3

Describe what caught your eye in this challenge

The Marketplace covers a wide range of different tools and there are useful training materials. However, it may be hard to navigate: it's not so accessible for lay SSH users. Only eight tools in the Marketplace are currently presented in Spanish. Besides, most tools include minimal or none descriptions. These descriptions do not include key information such as level of complexity.

We propose 1) to identify current problems in user experience, 2) to provide and design a prototype with icons for different levels of difficulty, and 3) to provide a sample of clear descriptions in Spanish for less tech-savvy users.

👥 Complutense Madrid team

Members

ADRIÁN MENÉNDEZ DE LA CUESTA GONZÁLEZ ES
Team lead

María Robles Pérez ES
Member

Amelia Sanz ES
Member

Apply to join this team

The ideas presented

Challenge 2A - Make the tools and resources of your community visible

Challenge 2A - Make the tools and resources of your community visible

⚡ Enlarge the scope toward european puppet plays texts !

Challenge 2A - Make the tools and resources of your community visible

0 3

Describe what caught your eye in this challenge

There are already some interesting datasets on the SSHOC MarketPlace dedicated to modern literature: the Brazilian Portuguese Literature Corpus in Portuguese, the Library of Southern Literature in Spanish, the Illinois 19th century corpus and Dramatic Structure and Social Status in Shakespeare's plays for English and the corpus of German-Language Fiction for German. The ERC PuppetPlays project (GA 835193) is currently gathering a 2000 references dataset describing precisely plays written for puppets in western Europe, from the 17th century to nowadays. This corpus of 2000 references also includes a sub-corpus of 300 works in full text, and not only the abstract, encoded in XML-TEI. Adding the PuppetPlays dataset to the MarketPlace, together with the NOVEL450 Corpus of western Europe texts, will allow SSHOC MarketPlace to offer to teachers, researchers or digital humanists a comprehensive corpus of various texts in many languages. The field of possibilities now opens up.

👥 Puppets and Literature

Members

Paul ROBERT FR
Team lead

Apply to join this team

The ideas presented

Challenge 2C - Reuse the SSH Open Marketplace data using the Application Programming Interface (API)

Challenge 2C - Reuse the SSH Open Marketplace data using the Application Programming Interface (API)

The Marketplace Pelican

Challenge 2C - Reuse the SSH Open Marketplace data using the Application Programming Interface (API)

0 ❤️ 3

Describe what caught your eye in this challenge

Following the well-known TEI Pelican, both a twitter bot (https://twitter.com/TEI_Pelican) and a static website (<https://teihub.netlify.app/>) made by Philip Allfray, I would like to create a script crawling through the public API of the MarketPlace (<https://marketplace-api.sshopencloud.eu/swagger-ui/index.html?url=/v3/api-docs/default/getDatasets>). Using queries like those already available (`get/api/datasets` and `get/api/publication` for example), it will look for specific terms ("puppets", "literature", "digital humanities",...) in the description of the JSON string returned by the API. Merging the SSHOC MarketPlace API with the current existing public API (CrossRef, Datacite, Isidore, Zenodo,...), I will be able to create my own database of publications and datasets related to a specific topic. This offers a very powerful tool for scientific monitoring.

The open science pelican

Members

 Paul Robert rs
Team lead

Apply to join this team

The ideas presented

Challenge 3A - I am preparing a training session on Open Science and looking for materials to reuse. Can I find these materials using the Training Discovery Toolkit (TDT)- and how can I reuse them?

Challenge 3A - I am preparing a training session on Open Science and looking for materials to reuse. Can I find these materials using the Training Discovery Toolkit (TDT)- and how can I reuse them?

The University Library helps you on your way to Openness

Challenge 3A - I am preparing a training session on Open Science and looking for materials to reuse. Can I find these materials using the Training Discovery Toolkit (TDT)- and how can I reuse them?

0 ❤️ 1

Describe what caught your eye in this challenge

My team is currently working on preparing training session on Open Science for the university. I am doing this challenge alone but will use the results in my team at home.

University Library Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam

Members

 Joeri Both NL
Team lead

Apply to join this team

The ideas presented

Challenge 3C - Play the SSHOC League of Data and learn how to Archive and Publish your research data.

Challenge 3C - Play the SSHOC League of Data and learn how to Archive and Publish your research data.

⚡ League of Data as a teaser for a data management training

Challenge 3C - Play the SSHOC League of Data and learn how to Archive and Publish your research data.

0 1

Describe what caught your eye in this challenge

When inviting data supporters and researchers for a data management training, it would be great if we could make them aware of basic knowledge around archiving and publishing research data and the overview presented in the Data Management Expert Guide. For this purpose I will have a closer look at the League of Data game. Basically the game should be fun and not raise questions, but already show how a researcher profits from data management.

PlayLoD

Members

- Ellen Leenarts NL**
Team lead

[Apply to join this team](#)

Links to the deliverables

Challenge 1

How to use VCR and Switchboard in teaching and training

Link to deliverable 1

Link to deliverable 2

Challenge 2A

Enlarge the scope towards european puppet plays texts!

Link to deliverable 1

Link to deliverable 2

Challenge 2A

Localisatie herenintus/Localising tools

Link to deliverable 1

Link to deliverable 2

Challenge 2C

The marketplace Policen

Link to deliverable 1

Link to deliverable 2

Challenge 3A

The University Library helps you on your way to Openness

Link to deliverable 1: N.A.

Link to deliverable 2

Challenge 2C

The Marketplace Policen

Link to deliverable 1

Link to deliverable 2

SSHOC Jury

Holly Wright

Karla Boesma

Veronika Heider

Evaluation results

User story name	AVG SCORE	Team	General rating	How effectively was the challenge addressed with the use of SSHOC tools?	How engaging is the user story told in the Milestones?	How inspiring are the tips & tricks for potential users?	How realistic are the recommendations for future improvement?
Localizando herramientas/Localizing tools	7.08	Complutense Madrid team	7.08	7.00	8.00	4.67	8.67
The University Library helps you on your way to Openness	6.42	University Library Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam	6.42	6.67	7.33	6.33	5.33
League of Data as a teaser for a data management training	6.17	PlayLoD	6.17	7.67	6.00	3.67	7.33
How to use VCR and Switchboard in teaching and training	6.08	Virtual teachers	6.08	6.33	6.00	6.33	5.67
The Marketplace Pelican	5.25	The open science pelican	5.25	6.67	5.67	3.33	5.33
Enlarge the scope toward european puppet plays texts!	4.5	Puppets and Literature	4.50	3.67	6.00	3.00	5.33

Winner of the 3rd prize!

Virtual Teachers

Janna Besamusca
Iulianna van der Lek
Nanette Rißler-Pipka

- Joint publication with the mentor organisation
- A 500€ Amazon gift voucher

Winner of the 3rd prize!

PlayLoD

Ellen Leenarts

- Joint publication with the mentor organisation
- A 500€ Amazon gift voucher

Winner of the 2nd prize!

**University Library Vrije
Universiteit Amsterdam**

Joeri Both

- Joint publication with the mentor organisation
- in-house training for up to 4 hours.
- A 500€ Amazon gift voucher

Winner of the 1st prize!

Complutense Madrid team

**Adrià Menéndez de la
Cuesta González
María Robles Pérez
Amelia Sanz**

- Joint publication with the mentor organisation.
- In-house SSHOC tool implementation for up to 4 hours.
- A 1000€ Amazon gift voucher

Survey

Request access to
the event survey
at [this link](#)

-
-
-

The image contains a graphic on the left showing a group of diverse people in profile, facing right, within a semi-circular frame. To the right of this graphic is the word "Survey" in bold. Further right is a purple rectangular box with a white top-right corner, containing the text "Request access to the event survey at [this link](#)". Below this text are three white horizontal lines, each preceded by a small white circle, representing a list or form fields.

Appendix 4 - Excerpts from the post-event survey

What did you like most about the conference?

the chance to interact with participants

Getting to know people I worked with online for more than 2 years only, connection to other EOSC science clusters and people outside SSHOC who were invited also

short presentations, variety of presentations

Catching new direction for the future in SSH in EOSC

The hybrid arrangement made the event very accessible

Getting to talk to peers again that I would normally not engage with. Seeing results from different sub projects.

I think the technical support for the hybrid mode was very well organized.

Informative about technical aspects

The smoothly combination of F2F and remote

very good presentations of the project results

the Quiz at the end & the SSHc & tell challenge & sl.do, the video testimonials

The policy session

Opportunity to meet after a long time with a number of colleagues in-person and have side-meetings.

Keeping track with the recent developments in policies and implementation of the EOSC.

Seeing each other after 2 year! Good speakers.

I liked that it was a hybrid conference

Ease of use of the digital platform

The organization of "live" sessions with lots of discussion

The speakers

Finally meeting my colleagues in real life! The food was amazing. It was well organised.

Interaction, discussions

Overall organisation was great

parallel session, multiple speakers per session

The conference was very informative. After participating the SSHOC Conference I came to know so many institutions are collaborating the SSHOC Consortium (27 Institutions) for research activities. The conference was open to all the people for dissemination information, open software for sharing the research data, published works etc.

Relevance for the field

It was nice to be at a real conference again.

The possibility to mingle again with colleagues informally around lunch/coffee

The content

In person opportunities for one-on-one discussion and information exchanges

Time between sessions to get to meet and talk with presenters/researchers

What did you miss or could be improved at the conference?
hybrid events are always tricky and time is lost with connection problems
compliments to the local organisers who very well combined the online and in person event
I noticed an imbalance between Social Sciences and Humanities (in the presentations)
To receive the list of in presence participants to make easier the connections
no
Nothing
may be a recap from the policy meetings at the end of the conference?
The lights were a bit dark in the room during the first session.
More discussion about data access (not just inter-operability and services).
The presentations in some sessions were too long. So, there was no time left for proper discussion with the audience
a bit better food
More significant participation of guests outside the project team(s).
I would have liked more video content & more games
The possibility to "virtually meet" colleagues during the coffee breaks
For online attendees, better technical support, the online service provider was absolutely awful. You need to have help support available during the conference if you intend to have it hybrid next year.
A first welcome round where everyone introduces themselves. Cuz there were small groups formed, mainly consisting of people that already knew each other.
A live chat
The location was a bit far out of the city centre. Just a minor point.
The programme was agreed really last minute, a bit more of advanced preparation would have been useful even if things eventually went out really well.
Seated dinner
Focused discussion on how to train next generations of researchers in the use of newly developed infrastructural tools

Your takeaway message or any other comments:
Make social sciences fair
SSHOC did well and I hope to continue working with some of its collaborators within EOSC Future and/or other projects
The outsourcing of the SSHOC'n Tell Challenge was a mistake! And people who are chairing or having a major role in organisation should be there in person

Although I participated online, very happy that meeting in person is again possible!
SSH should absolutely continue in developing the cluster and work together inside of the scientific knowledge; SSHOC is a great achievement.
Thank you for the excellent organisation!
Thank you!
Great opportunity to meet with people in person, finally!
The conference was very informative, thank you for organizing!
I learnt less than I had hoped.
was a great event. Happy to have attended.
Thank you for organising!
Thank you.
great experience, thanks
Well done!
the conference gave a good overview of what SSHOC has achieved
thanks to all organisers
The sustainability aspect is crucial for any final event for the the proejct & this is important to have this discussed at length.
The cluster cooperation should continue, one way or another, as this is the way forward
The EOSC activities can be meaningful and effective; social sciences and humanities are on good track.
Although I'm not sure how the online participants liked the conference, the in person part was great.
Thank you for organising it
I was very lucky to work on this project in different tasks. It has been an honor and a pleasure to work at these very high levels. I will keep an exceptional memory of this experience. Thanks. Maurizio Sanesi
SSHOC was a great experience for SSH Infrastructures! A cluster developed remotely during the time of COVID-19 has shown that is possible to conduct projects in "new" ways
For online attendees, better technical support, the online service provider was absolutely awful. You need to have help support available during the conference if you intend to have it hybrid next year.
It was a good experience being part of such an international and diverse team in the SSHOC project. Thank you. <3
Great conference :)
none

I have learned SSHOC provides a fully fledged Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud where data, tools, and training are available to #SSH Communities as part of #EOSC.

Social science representation could have been improved

Great organization, all went very smooth. Thanks a lot.

Thanks for all the hard work to make the conference happen!

Well done that online participation in sessions went so smoothly

SSHOC and EOSC are great ventures but still to little focused on ordinary (rank and file) researchers. Risk remains that the tools and services developed will remain out of reach for large groups of researchers.

FAIR data and "we are toasters"

Well organized, interesting topics.

Great that you set this up as a hybrid conference; and that you had panel discussions.

SSHOC results well presented